

**ROBOTOTEXNIKA SOHASINI MAKTABLARDA JORIY QILISH
SAMARADORLIGI**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada robototexnik qurilmalar, Arduino UNO platalari yordamida qurilmalarni ulash va ularni darslik sifatida kiritish samaradorligi haqida fikr-mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Arduino, UNO, sketch, interfeys, robot, datchik, PID kutubxonasi, sensor, robototexnika, transport.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the effectiveness of robotic devices, connecting devices using Arduino UNO boards and entering them as a textbook.

Keywords: Arduino, UNO, sketch, interface, robot, sensor, PID library, sensor, robotics, transport.

KIRISH

Mamlakatimizda kompyuter texnologiyasini o'rganishga oid darslik va qo'llanmalar istagancha topiladi. Biroq robototexnika fanini o'rganish hali yetarli darajada yo'lga qo'yilmagan. Holbuki, robototexnikani o'zlashtirmasdan dunyo

taraqqiyotiga qo'shilib, uning yutuqlariga erishib bo'lmaydi. Shu boisdan ham umumiy o'rta ta'lim hamda o'rta maxsus va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida robototexnika alohida dars sifatida o'qitilishi zamon talabiga aylanib ulgurdi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Robototexnik qurilmalarni yig'ish bilan birga ularni dasturlash masalasi ham ancha murakkab jarayon hisoblanadi. Odatda robototexnik qurilmalarga dasturlar Arduino platasi yordamida yoziladi.

Arduino - bu o'ziga xos protsessor va xotiraga ega bo'lgan kichik plata bolib, professional bo'lmagan foydalanuvchilarga mo'ljallangan oddiy avtomatlashtirish va robototexnika tizimlarini yaratish uchun mo'ljallangan apparat va dasturiy ta'minot brendidir.

Dasturiy ta'minot qismi dasturlarni yozish, kompilyatsiya qilish va dasturiy ta'minot uchun bepul dasturiy qobiqdan iborat. Uskuna qismi rasmiy ishlab chiqaruvchilar tomonidan sotiladigan oldindan yig'ilgan bosma elektron platalar

to'plamidir. To'liq ochiq tizim arxitekturasi sizga Arduino mahsulotlar qatoriga bemalol nusxa ko'chirish yoki qo'shish imkoniyatini beradi.

MUHOKAMA

Arduinodan avtomatlashtirilgan ob'ektlarni yaratish yoki standart simli va simsiz interfeyslar orqali kompyuterda dasturiy ta'minotga ulanish uchun foydalanish mumkin.

Robototexnik qurilmalarga quyidagi mikrokontrollerlarni misol qilishimiz mumkin: Arduino platalari, Father simlari, Breadboard taxtasi, PIR datchiklar, Svetodiodlar, Fotodiodlar, Sensor datchiklar va boshqalar. Arduino IDE ga yozilgan kodlar sketch deb ataladi. Arduinoga sketch yozish uchun uni kompyuterga Arduino USB orqali bog'lab olish kerak. Sketchlar orqali biz Arduino platalariga dasturlar yozib qurilmalar vazifalarini kiritishimiz mumkin.

Robotlar kelajakning ko'zga ko'ringan suniy intellektlaridan biri sanaladi. Shu asosida o'zini o'zi muvozanatlaydigan bir qancha loyihalar yaratilgan. Bu esa robototexnikaning shiddat bilan rivojlanayotganiga bir misoldir. Robototexnika - har qanday bola uchun eng yangi va istiqbolli mashg'ulotlaridan biri hisoblanadi.

NATIJA

Ushbu kursda o'quvchilarga robotlarni va boshqa obyektlarni qurish va yaratish to'g'risidagi bilimlar beriladi. Bu Internet-texnologiyalari yo'nalishidagi sohadir. Robot nazorati ostida o'zi hal qilgan muammolar qatoriga moslashish, harakatlarni dasturlash, boshqarish tizimi va uning dasturiy ta'minotini sintez qilish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan murakkab vazifalarni hal etishni nazarda tutadi.

Boshqarish turi bo'yicha robot tizimlari quyidagilarga bo'linadi. Biotexnik:

- buyruq (alohida robot havolalarining tugmachasini va qo'lini boshqarish);
- nusxa ko'chirish (odamning harakatini takrorlash, qo'llaniladigan kuchni, ekzoskeletlarni uzatuvchi teskari aloqani amalga oshirish mumkin);
- yarim avtomatik (bitta buyruq tanasini boshqarish, masalan, robotning butun kinematik sxemasi dastagi);

Avtomatik:

- dasturiy ta'minot (oldindan belgilangan dastur asosida ishlaydi, asosan doimiy atrof-muhit sharoitida bir xildagi vazifalarni hal qilish uchun mo'ljallangan);
- adaptiv (ular odatdagi vazifalarni hal qilishadi, lekin ishlash sharoitlariga moslashadi);
- aqlli (eng zamonaviy avtomatik tizimlar); Interaktiv:
- avtomatlashtirilgan (avtomatik va biotexnik rejimlarni almashtirish mumkin);
- nazorat (odam faqat maqsadni belgilash funktsiyalarini bajaradigan avtomatik tizimlar);

- dialog (robot o'zini tutish strategiyasini tanlash uchun odam bilan muloqotda qatnashadi, qoida tariqasida robot manipulyatsiya natijalarini bashorat qilishga va maqsadni tanlash bo'yicha maslahat berishga qodir mutaxassis tizimi bilan jihozlangan). Robotlarni boshqarishning asosiy vazifalari qatoriga quyidagilar kiradi:

- rejalashtirish qoidalari;
- harakatlarni rejalashtirish;
- rejalashtirish kuchlari va momentlari;
- dinamik aniqlik tahlili;
- robotning kinematik va dinamik xususiyatlarini aniqlash.

Robotlarni boshqarish usullarini ishlab chiqishda texnik kibernetika yutuqlari va avtomatik boshqarish nazariyasi katta ahamiyatga ega.
XULOSA

Shuni qayd etish lozimki, robototexnika fanini ta'lim tizimiga izchillik bilan joriy etish kelajakda yoshlarning zamon talablariga mos fikrlash doirasining shakllanishiga zamin yaratadi. Qolaversa, nafaqat robototexnika sohasi, balki iqtisodiyotning boshqa turli tizimlari rivojlanishiga ham kuchli turtki beradi.

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